

A sensitive, selective and extractive spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI) using 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran

Joginder Rohilla and R. K. Baweja*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

E-mail : jogi001s@gmail.com; jogi001@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 24 July 2007, accepted 30 July 2007

Abstract : A simple, rapid, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of tungsten(VI) in trace amounts is developed using 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPB) as a reagent for the complexation of metal ion and extracting the 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex into dichloromethane from 1 M HCl solution. It obeys Beer's law in the range 0–2.7 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity at 391 nm as $4.29 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00434 \mu\text{g W cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The method is free from the interference of a large number of elements (39).

Keywords : Spectrophotometric, extraction, tungsten(VI).

There are various spectrophotometric methods which suffer from low sensitivity, non-selectivity and complexity in the procedures for the determination of tungsten in trace amounts using thiocyanate, vanadophosphoric acid and dithiol¹. Other reported methods using several organic reagents for this purpose also suffer from one or more of these drawbacks². This has appreciated to search for new better methods and accordingly, 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPB) has been used as a complexing agent for tungsten(VI) in the spectrophotometric determination of metal ion to meet the above requirements.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : The absorbance of the W^{VI} -HPB complex in dichloromethane was greatly influenced by the nature of acids. From 1 M acidity fixed in each case, the absorbance was found to decrease in the order : HCl (0.230) > H_2SO_4 (0.200) > HClO_4 (0.190) > HNO_3 (0.180) > CH_3COOH (0.130). The complex gave very low absorbance (0.010) in the alkaline medium as observed with NaOH (0.2 M). Therefore, HCl medium was preferred for further studies.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : Various organic solvents namely dichloromethane, 1,2-dichloroethane, chloroform, toluene, benzene, isobutyl methyl ketone, carbon tetra chloride, isoamyl alcohol, ethyl acetate, isoamyl acetate and cyclohexane extracted the W^{VI} -HPB complex in the decreasing order of absorbance. As dichloromethane gave maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation,

it was chosen as the most suitable extractant. A single equilibrium of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane under conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of W^{VI} -HPB complex.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorbance spectrum of the complex indicated that the maximum lied at 389–394 nm in the visible region, where the reagent blank also show some absorbance. In dichloromethane, the absorbance remains unchanged for more than 20 h at 391 nm.

Effect of concentration of HCl, HPB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The optimum values of above parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.9–2.5 M HCl, 0.6–1.6 ml of 0.05% HPB (in acetone) and 5–240 s equilibration time for $\leq 27 \mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}}$ per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of the reagent and HCl should be kept throughout same as per proposed procedure as on changing this order, low absorbance is observed.

Beer's law range, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and composition of the complex : Beer's law was valid in the concentration range of 0–2.75 $\mu\text{g W}^{\text{VI}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$. However, the optimum range for the determination of tungsten, as evaluated from Ringbom plot³, was calculated to be 0.50–2.69 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 391 nm were $4.29 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00434 \mu\text{g W cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The ratio of W^{VI} and HPB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 2 by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburg and

Cooper for a two phase system⁴. This was further confirmed by the mole ratio and equilibrium shift methods⁵. On the basis of the spectrophotometric methods the most probable structure of the W^{VI}-HPB complex is as given below :

W^{VI}-HPB complex

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in parantheses), chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate, nitrate, sulphate, sulphite and thiourea (100 each), phosphate, dithionite, sulfosalicylic acid (70 each); thiocyanate, ascorbic acid (50 each); carbonate (20); tartarate (10); EDTA (5); fluoride (0.5); glycerol (1 ml); H₂O₂ (6% w/v) (0.3 ml) were without effect. However, oxalate and citrate even in traces interfered seriously. Among the cations Ca^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ni^{II}, Hg^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II} (10 each); Al^{III}, Bi^{III} (8 each); Be^{II}, Cu^{II}, U^{VI}, Se^{IV}, Ce^{IV}, As^{III} (5 each); Os^{VIII} (3); Sn^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Pd^{II} (1 each); Cr^{VI}, Pt^{III} (0.5 each); Ru^{II} (0.4), Re^{VII} (0.3), Ir^{III}, Ta^V, Au^{III} (0.1 each), Zr^{IV} (0.04) caused < 1% error in absorbance. Fe^{III}, V^V and Mo^{VI} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Application : The wide applicability of the method was tested by carrying out the analysis of various synthetic samples with satisfactory results. The proposed spectrophotometric method is highly selective, sensitive and free from the interference of a large number of analytically important metal ions. The results obtained were highly reproducible with a standard deviation of ± 0.0019 absorbance units.

Experimental

A Shimadzu 140-02 (UV-Vis) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. A standard stock solution (100 ml) of tungsten(vi) containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amounts (0.179 g) of sodium tungstate (A.R., C.D.H.) in deionized water and standardized by the oxine method¹. Lower concentrations at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level were prepared by suitable dilution there from. Solutions of other ions were prepared at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level by dissolving there sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acids. They were suitably diluted to

obtain lower concentrations of the metal ions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level. Hydrochloric acid (1 M) was prepared by diluting the acid with deionized water. 3-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPB), m.p. 171–172 °C was synthesized by the literature method and dissolved in acetone to get 0.05% (w/v) solution⁶. Dichloromethane (Ranbaxy) was used as such. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing a known volume of tungsten(vi) solution with solutions of other metal ions in suitable proportions.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing $\leq 27 \mu\text{g}$ tungsten(vi) and other ions taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel were added 1 M hydrochloric acid (1 ml), 0.05% (w/v) HPB in acetone (1 ml) and sufficient deionized water to make up the volume to 10 ml. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane for 30 s. The light yellow organic phase was separated. The absorbance of the complex in the extract was measured at 391 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the amount of tungsten was determined from the standard curve prepared in an analogous manner. For 0.1 mg Fe^{III} was added 20 mg 'disodium' EDTA, for each of the 0.04 mg Mo^{VI} and V^V was added 0.25 ml 6% (w/v) H₂O₂, as masking agents, before the addition of HPB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of W-complex

HCl (M) ^a	0.02	0.06	0.08	0.09–0.25	0.28	0.30
Absorbance	0.155	0.190	0.200	0.230	0.210	0.190
0.05% HPB (ml) ^b	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6–1.6	1.8	2.0
Absorbance	0.150	0.190	0.210	0.230	0.190	0.180
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	2	5–240			
Absorbance	0.080	0.130	0.230			

^aW^{VI} = 10 μg , HCl = variable, 0.05% HPB = 1 ml, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = dichloromethane, aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml, number of extractions = 1.

^bHCl = 0.1 M, other conditions being same as in (a) except for the variation in HPB concentration also HPB = 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran.

^c0.05% (w/v) HPB in acetone = 1 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Acknowledgement

Our sincere thanks are due to Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. K. Kodama, "Methods of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1963, p. 420; E. B. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metal", 3rd ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 883; F. D. Snell, "Photometric and Fluorometric Methods of Analysis", Part 2, Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 1265; Z. Marezenko, "Spectrophotometric

- Determination of Elements", 2nd ed., New York, 1986.
- Anita. A. Wahi, A. K. Chakkar and L. R. Kakkar, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1996, **19**, 12; S. P. Bag, A. K. Chakrabarti and G. P. Goswami, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India*, 2000, **70A**, 157; N. Agnihotri and J. R. Mehta, *Annali di Chimica*, 2004, **94**, 341; G. Aodeng, F. Bao and S. Yin, *Yejin Fenxi*, 2002, **22**, 42; R. Agnihotri, Raj Kamal, N. Agnihotri and J. R. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 728.
 - A. Ringbom, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
 - W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
 - H. P. Tarasiewicz, A. Grundniewska and M. Tarasiewicz, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **94**, 435; R. Agnihotri, N. Agnihotri and J. R. Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 842.
 - R. M. Moriarty, Om Prakash and H. A. Musallam, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1985, **22**, 583.